

ISic2716

I.Sicily inscription 2716

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museum or catacomb Antiquarium

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

0. [---]

1. [---][---]

2. [---]HHM[---]

3. [---]ENA[---]

4. [---]KAMM[---]

5. [---]EN

5a. □

Apparatus

Text after Griesheimer 1996

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645136

PHI 333383

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1996.0803

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 46.1287

Griesheimer, M. 1996. Nouvelles inscriptions funéraires de la catacombe Saint-Jean. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana.* 72: 115-132. At 123 no.7 fig.7

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic2716. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354983>